

HISTORY OF LEXICOGRAPHY

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Annation : This article discusses lexicography and its history and origin. In addition, the basics of lexicography were also discussed.

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Lexicography is a branch of lexicology that studies the principles of creating a dictionary. The branch of science that studies the semantic structure of words, the properties of words, and their interpretation. Applied lexicography performs socially important functions that provide language teaching, language description and normalization, interlinguistic communication, scientific study of language. Lexicography seeks to find the most appropriate and acceptable ways to perceive all knowledge about the language to reflect the vocabulary. Macrocore of theoretical lexicography (vocabulary selection, vocabulary and nature, principles of location of material) and microstructure of the dictionary (structure of the dictionary entry, types of dictionary definitions, ratio of different information about the word , types of linguistic illustrations, etc.) includes a set of problems: with the creation of a typology of dictionaries, with the history of lexicography. All dictionaries are divided into two main types: encyclopedic and linguistic, or linguistic. In monolingual dictionaries, words are explained using words of the same language. Monolingual dictionaries are complex and aspectual. Consolidated glossaries. Such dictionaries contain information necessary for understanding the word, its use in speech, and others. Aspect dictionaries reflect one or another aspect of the language. These include: dictionaries of foreign words, synonyms, antonyms, homonyms, paronyms, phraseological, orthoepic, spelling, derivative, morphemic, etymological, reverse, abbreviations and other types of dictionaries. Each dictionary has an introduction that explains how to use the dictionary. From the first small hand-written dictionaries for various peoples, the road to multi-volume printed publications has developed on its way. In the first period of the development of lexicographic practice, most European nations developed only individual elements of future dictionaries. In the so-called pre-glossary period, such elements were glosses (from the Greek glossa - an obsolete or little-used word). They were a translation or interpretation of an obscure word or phrase. These comments and translations are made in the margins or directly in the text of the book. For the first time in the Western European tradition, the Greeks began to use glosses in the study of Homeric poetry. Later glosses some parts of the Bible, legal texts, literary

began to be widely used in the interpretation of monuments. The historical development of the vocabulary of a particular language can be observed in historical and etymological dictionaries. Dictionaries include information related to the history of words in a particular language, usually found in written records. Historical dictionaries started by the Grimm brothers and published for more than a hundred years (1854-1961), "Materials for a dictionary of the Old Russian language from written monuments" (1893-1912) by I.I. Sreznevsky, "Dictionary of the Russian language of the 11th-17th centuries.", "Historical Slounics of the Belarusian language" in many volumes, which is not yet completed, etc.

Etymological dictionaries contain information about the motivation of the oldest meanings of words, along with the main forms. Lexicography is a very delicate and long-term labor. Studying the meaning of the vocabulary of all languages, lexical units, is one of the main goals of general linguistics. In the next period, in terms of lexicology, attention is being paid to

the study of the system of nominative units of the language, synonyms and functional features. After all, perfect learning of the language with the help of lexicography, which provides extensive information about the lexicon and lexical units, becoming aware of the language features, determining the linguistic essence of the language units, determining the connections between professionalism and professional communication, and developing criteria for distinguishing various functional and methodological areas of the language are of great importance. The English name of the annotated dictionary comes from the Latin word. For over 300 years, no English word has been in any dictionary. Most dictionaries in England are written to help people learning Latin. The titles of these books are really meaningful. For example, such as "Storage for the little ones" or "Garden of words". In 1552, the first dictionary of English words compiled by Richard Haloet was published. The title of the dictionary was long: Absedarium Anglico-Latinum pro Tirunculis. As you can see, this book is also titled in Latin. It differed from other dictionaries in that every English word was written first with an English explanation and then with a Latin translation. The dictionary is recognized as the first English annotated dictionary because it first comes with annotated English words. The dictionary "Absedarium" consisted of 26,000 words. It was very popular but extremely expensive. As a result, many similar books have been published that are small in size but affordable for the average reader. At that time, dictionary compilers did not annotate all the words in the English language, but only the most complex ones. The first book called "English Annotated Dictionary" was compiled in 1623 by Henry Cockerham. In 1807, Noah Webster began work on a huge dictionary in the United States. This dictionary was published in 1828 and contained 12,000 words and 40,000 definitions. No one had done this before Webster, who simplified the spelling of difficult words quite a bit, which is why some English words are spelled differently in England and America.

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